

MICRO-CRACK DETECTION TECHNIQUE IN POLYMERIC COMPOSITES DURING THERMAL CYCLING

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ABSTRACT

Carbon-fiber reinforced polymeric composite materials have been widely used in space industry for manufacturing of spacecraft structures, satellite-panels and antennas. In space, composites are subjected to the periodic thermal cycling (TC) in which temperature ranges from -196 to 180°C , depending on operational condition. This range of temperatures causes various damages in composite, such as micro cracks, which in turn reduce the composite life cycles. Usually the micro-cracks become more evident/detectable when subjected to high number of thermal cycles. The aim of this work is to develop a technique to be able to identify the micro-crack initiation and its propagation at low number of thermal cycles. Experimental tests were conducted on composite specimens by subjecting the samples to thermal shock from -190°C (dipping in liquid nitrogen) to $+150^{\circ}\text{C}$ with different number of cycles, then optical microscope was used to observe the micro-cracks. The microscopic results show that few micro-cracks appeared on the surface with low number of thermal cycles. Samples are then conditioned in boiled distil water to become saturated (moisture procedure). A fast cooling, followed by sample drying in oven above water boiling temperature was performed and the samples were again examined under microscope. It was observed that the previous existing micro-cracks are more visible and also some new micro cracks surfaced. It is suggested that in order to detect the micro-cracks during the thermal cycling, moisture and heat can be used to accelerate the micro-crack growth and make them detectable even at low number of thermal cycles.

Keywords: Thermal cycling, Moisture, Composites, Micro-crack initiation,

1 INTRODUCTION

Reinforced polymeric composites with high strength and low density are an alternative candidate in lightweight structures in the aerospace industry. One of the most important advantages of composite materials are their high strength-to-weight ratios, low density, low CTE, high reliability in stiffness and their inherent high thermal/temperature resistance [1]. Replacing conventional metal alloys with composites, especially in satellites, aircraft and other automotive applications, results in considerable weight savings. The objective is usually to make a component which meets the design requirements and often with a low density for longer sustainability (longer time period).

In recent years, structural parts manufactured with carbon/epoxy polymeric composite materials have been widely used in space and aircraft industries [2–4]. In the case of satellites, temperatures can often vary by near 270°C or above as they orbit around the earth [5–8]. A satellite in eclipse region, (Earth's shadow) can experience temperatures as low as -190°C , from 150°C in sunlit region. This phenomenon is known as thermal cycling in a cryogenic environment and is extensively found to induce micro-cracking, one of the main damage mechanisms of composite materials undergoing thermal cycling.

Thermal stresses are generated during the temperature variation and curing processes of composite materials. But in addition, moisture can induces/produce different effects such as matrix properties reductions, swelling and expansion of matrix at the fiber-matrix interface that modifies the state of residual stresses and causes the micro-crack formation in composite materials [9–11]. It is known, that the moisture has significant effects on the physical and chemical properties of epoxy matrix as well as on their final performance of composite structures especially in their long-term utilization. The absorbed water usually reduces the glass-transition temperature (T_g) by plasticizing the polymer

network and also affects mechanical performance and long-term durability of high performance composites.

Manufacturing method is an influential factor in composite material properties. Composite structures are often cured in an autoclave to achieve the required space grade quality. However, curing large structures need access to large autoclaves which is limited and expensive. So fabrication of large structures using OOA prepreg materials will result in huge amount of savings in manufacturing costs [12]. In OOA manufacturing method, presence of voids has been an issue due to lack of high pressure onto the laminate to eliminate the voids. As an alternative, a vacuum pump is utilized to exert a low pressure for minimizing the void content [13]. Many researchers have compared OOA prepreps with autoclave materials and found that the properties of laminates fabricated with the OOA prepreps can be the same as those fabricated with autoclave prepreps [14-15]. Caubergths et al. [16] studied the OOA manufacturing of aerospace representative parts with complex shape using carbon/epoxy prepreg technology and compared them with autoclave parts. The mechanical performance of OOA prepreps including compression and bending properties was comparable to autoclave prepreps and both techniques yielded to void free parts. Achieving uniformity in the thickness around tight corners was reported to be challenging for both techniques. Therefore, the purpose of this research work is to study the mechanical and thermal properties of out-of-autoclave (OOA) carbon fiber epoxy composite after thermal cycling.

Thermal cycling or thermal-shocking can be defined as a process of rapid changes in the temperature of the specimen from low to high or vice versa [10]. There is a lack of information in the literature and experiments need to be conducted to study the combined effects of thermal and moisture cycling loading. Space environments have a range of temperatures that cause damage in parts made of composite materials which affect their performance and even threaten their ability to operate effectively for recommended time period. The second challenge is the orientation and lay-up of composite materials to delay the damage. Therefore, each orientation or lay-up has their own individual strength against environmental effects. The third challenge is how to analyze and simulate material behavior during test procedures, both analytically and numerically. Overall here first priority will be given to identify the cracks and their propagation at low number of cycles, and then improve their life cycles or delay the damages with optimizing orientations/lay-up.

2 THE GENERAL CONCEPT FOR MICROSCOPIC CRACKS IDENTIFICATION

The motivation for this paper is to develop a method to make micro cracks visible and detectable at early stage of thermal cycling of a polymeric composite. The concern and necessity for such a method was raised by the space/aerospace industries. Currently most of the structures in satellites or supersonic aircraft are made of composite materials or a combination of polymer components and alloys. These structures can present significant challenges for manufacturing, but most challenges are found during their service life in fluctuating environments. Even as we consider that during manufacturing, structures contain acceptable defects or micro-cracks because of limitations in testing equipment. Micro-cracks usually become more visible and detectable at higher numbers of thermal cycling. Furthermore, the identification of micro-cracks which are considered negligible and their intensive propagation at early stage is mechanically rigorous but consequently has great potential for use in manufacturing design for complex space/aerospace applications in varying environments.

Accelerated test method is used to save time and get the approximate results to predict the damage condition for long-term behavior in short period. Accelerated (temperature dependent) tests are justifiable if the accelerating parameter does not cause an artificial change in the aging mechanism. To verify this assumption, tests on a reasonably long time scale are necessary. The data in [21] indicated that 1000 h of accelerated aging at 70 °C caused a loss in flexural properties similar to 14 -15 years in natural conditions. This is one of very few examples for which the effect of accelerated aging has been verified. Based on results of this example, proposed experimental methods of accelerated test were

conducted and no damage was induced by accelerated parameters. The details procedure is described as follows.

3 SAMPLE PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENT

3.1 Material Selection

The material used for this project was Cycom 5320-1 manufactured by Cytec Engineered Materials Inc. which is a composite material system for manufacturing of primary structural parts in today's aerospace industry. It is a toughened epoxy prepreg system specifically designed for OOA manufacturing. A woven fabric of 5-harness carbon/epoxy satin prepreg (5HS) with the same resin system provided by Cytec was used to manufacture the samples, with total laminate thickness of ~3.5 mm.

3.2 Manufacturing of the OOA Samples

The laminates were made a cross-ply laminate with 8 layers of 5HS woven fabric (5-harness satin prepreps). The plate was manufactured by the hand layup method and was vacuumed at a pressure of 0.1 MPa for one hour to eliminate the entrapped air and moisture. To track the plate temperature during the curing process and afterwards during the thermal cycling process, a k-type thermocouple was bonded to the edge of the mid plane of the laminate. Since the carbon fibers are conductive and by touching the thermocouple can cause false temperature reading, a release film was utilized to avoid contact between the prepreg and the thermocouple wire.

To cure the composite laminate, the cure cycle recommended by the manufacturer for Cycom 5320-1 material system was followed to cure the composite laminates [22]. The material was cured in a forced air circulation oven. A vacuum pump was used to pull the vacuum inside the layup bag. In order to accurately measure the laminate temperature during the cure and avoid the temperature delay between the oven temperature and plate temperature, the other end of the thermocouple already embedded in the laminate mid-plane was taken out of the oven and used for a data acquisition system. It was assumed that once the center ply of the laminate was within ± 5 °C of the desired temperature, all plies of the laminate had reached temperature equilibrium. Figure 1(a)-(b), shows OOA set-up and the cure cycle for the composite plate. As shown in this figure, the oven temperature was ramped from the room temperature to 120 °C and held at this temperature for 3 hours to cure the epoxy. Then it was raised to 177 °C and maintained at same temperature kept for 2 hours for the post-curing, and finally the plate was allowed to cool down to room temperature. All the temperature changes occurred at a ramp rate of 0.6–2.8 °C/min (Figure 1b).

Figure 1: a) Manufacturing set-up for OOA curing inside oven, b) Measured data and recommended cure cycle by material supplier.

3.3 Thermal Cycling

Extreme thermal cycling was applied on samples with dimensions corresponding to a width, length and thickness of $30 \times 12 \times 3$ mm respectively, using a “thermal shock” method. The samples were dipped in liquid nitrogen (-195°C) for a period of 2 min and then exposed to room temperature (20°C) for a period of 5 min. Then the samples are heated up inside the oven to 150°C and maintained for 10 minutes as shown in Figure 2(a). This procedure will be repeated for up to 10, 50, 100, 150 and 200 cycles as shown in the Figure 2(b). Selected samples were taken under microscope after thermal cycles at 50, 100, 150 and 200. One side of the every sample was polished to make smooth surface for microscopic inspection. Different cross-section were marked for inspection of laminates layers, micro-cracks, voids, resin rich area and their locations in layers or tows.

Figure 2. a) Thermal cycle time steps, b) Temperature cycle vs. time for 10 + thermal cycles

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cross-sectional regions in each sample were examined under microscopic with 10-20X-magnification to track the cracks/damage in the entire sample and to detect the presence of micro-cracks. After this, every single layer were observed at specific locations for analysis of the path of the crack. During image analysis, we were also focused on crack onsets which appear in the form of voids which would result in cracks/delamination on the inner and outer ply of the composite laminate. Figure 3(a) shows selection of cross-sectional area, here no micro-cracks are visible. But there are some void, that's could be the cause for cracks initiation under thermal cycles. Later we observed in Figure 3(b), which is 100^{th} thermal cycles where no initiation of cracks was detected, but as cycles increased to 200^{th} , the cracks become slightly visible. It doesn't mean that the micro-cracks appeared suddenly near 200^{th} cycles. It could be there but as residual stresses increased by “thermal shock” like cooling and heating, aided to open the shield surface as a micro-crack.

Figure 3: Micrograph and crack detection a) before thermal shocking, b) after 200 thermal cycles

From examination of the microscope image analysis, there were two situations may occur. First, by continuation of the thermal cycle process and allowing the micro-cracks to propagate which is more time consuming. Secondly, from the theory of composite materials, as we know that the matrix is the weak-link in the composite, especially because resins do not presently exist that allow the utilization of the stresses that fibers are able to withstand. The matrix plays a minor role in the load-carrying (tensile) capacity of a composite structure. However, the matrix serves the purpose of providing resistance to crack propagation and damage on interface of fiber-matrix as well as influencing the compressive, interlaminar shear and in-plane shear properties of the composite. Additionally, the way in which composite materials absorb moisture depends upon factors such as temperature, fiber volume fraction, layup-orientation, fiber contained (that is, permeability, polarity, density), area of exposed surfaces, diffusivity, and surface protection. So with this knowledge of the factors influencing absorption of moisture, we conduct moisture procedure, for accelerated the crack propagation.

An accelerated moisture cycle is designed, which is expected to cause a very similar micro-crack response in the material as the baseline environment, but in a much shorter time. Accelerated moisture cycle involves thermal cycling and drying in an oven, then the specimens were immersed in distilled water in a glass vessel which is in turn immersed in boiled oil, with the temperature which has been controlled by heater from the Heidolph MR Hei-Standard Company.

In order to measure the amount of water absorbed by each sample, the specimen weight has been measured periodically by an analytical balance (Sartorius Company) which is accurate to ~0.1 mg. Before weighing, the specimens was wiped with a paper towel and dried for approximately 1-2 min to remove any excess surface moisture and to avoid the error caused by specimen heat modifying the zero balance. The weight and conditioning time are recorded to calculate the moisture content. The moisture content has been plotted as the weight gain against the square root of conditioning time. The weight of the wet conditioned specimen decreases as the measuring time increases. For example, within 3-6 hours, the moisture content of samples can change from 0.05% to 0.5%. The thickness of each specimen was determined as the average of four measurements near each end. The width and the length will be measured as the average of two edges. Specimen weight has been measured every 6 hours until saturation happened or until more than 1% of moisture weight has been gained as shown below Figure 4.

Figure 4. Weight Gain of the samples as a Function of time

All the water, which was absorbed by matrix, inside cavity, void, interface laminate layers will increase the density or expand the samples. The measurement by the weight shows that the all samples were saturated, then we took next step to freeze the samples by immersing in the liquid nitrogen (-195

$^{\circ}\text{C}$). Time period for freezing was 2-3 min and bring it back to room temperature. After freezing, the microcracks in the samples were analyzed under microscope to investigate again the crack propagation. Through the image analysis we observed onset cracks, which were more prominent as shown in Figure 5(a).

After the examination of the frozen samples under microscope, samples were dried by heating them above 100°C in oven. Dried sample were again examined under microscope and it was observed that the cracks grew and become larger. This process can force the cracks to open more and therefore more invisible cracks might become visible as shown in Figure 5(b).

Onset cracks developed by thermal cycling get saturated faster (during saturation processes) that help to accelerate crack propagation. These saturated samples are immersed in liquid nitrogen to freeze the saturated water in their own cavity or over void surfaces. Initial cracks are propagated faster during drying processes as saturated liquid expand their volume under increasing temperatures.

Figure 5: Crack detection a) after moisture saturation and freezing and b) after drying.

Most of the research on crack initiation and propagation is conducted using thermal and moisture cycle individually or combination of both that takes more time and longer processing. Through this proposal, two extra steps (freeze and dry) are added to save time by accelerating the cracks propagation. The micro-scale cracks has been shown to evolve faster and earlier to macro-cracks and in a larger quantity in the presence of voids. Considering the locations of stress concentration, such micro-cracks were detected at both void tips and above voids that lie right beneath the surface. We have noted that microcracks are developed from the voids in resin rich area as shown in Figure 3 and 5. This is primarily due to the higher stress concentration as a result of two factors, firstly, the free body thermal strain and secondly swelling strain as a result of moisture absorption. Based on the microscopic image analysis, it is evident that the crack propagation is accelerated (less number of thermal cycles to form cracks) due to the presence of moisture, which is absorbed during the immersion of samples in water (moisture procedure), this is as a result of expansion of moisture (swelling) around the void, after the sample is heated in the dry/hot cycle.

We have also noted that the edge affects also needs to be taken into account, a complex stress state exists between the layers of different orientation at the free edge of a laminate, and the edge could be in the form of a straight edge or a perimeter of a hole. When a laminate is subjected to thermal or mechanical strain the end of the cut fibers must transfer the load (temperature or moisture) to adjacent fibers. The matrix is the only mechanism for this load transfer. The stresses due to this load, namely interlaminar stresses, can be sufficient to cause local microcracking and edge delamination.

5 CONCLUSION

Experimental tests were conducted on composite specimens by subjecting the samples to thermal shock from -190 °C (dipping in liquid nitrogen) to +150 °C with different number of cycles. Using optical microscope, the micro-cracks were detected particularly around the voids. The microscopic results show that few micro-cracks appeared on the surface with low number of thermal cycles. Moisture and freezing are used to make micro-cracks more visible. Samples are then conditioned in boiled water to become saturated (moisture procedure). A fast cooling followed by sample drying in oven above water boiling temperature was performed and the samples were examined under microscope again. It was observed that the previous existing micro-cracks are more visible and also some new micro cracks surfaced. It is demonstrated that, to detect the micro-cracks at low number of thermal cycles, moisture and heat can be used to accelerate the micro-crack growth and make them more detectable.

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REFERENCES

- [1] W. D. Callister and D. G. Rethwisch, "Materials science nad engineering: An introduction," *Mach. Sci. Technol.*, 2009.
- [2] S. Rouquie, M. C. Lafarie-Frenot, J. Cinquin, and a. M. Colombaro, "Thermal cycling of carbon/epoxy laminates in neutral and oxidative environments," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 65, no. 3–4, pp. 403–409, 2005.
- [3] R. A. Schapery, "Thermal Expansion Coefficients of Composite Materials Based on Energy Principles," *Composites*, vol. 15, no. 2, p. 161, 1984.
- [4] G. Yu, D. Shang-Li, H. Song, Y. De-Zhuang, and L. Zhi-Jun, "Characterization of Stress Distribution and Thermal Expansion Behavior for M40J/AG-80 Composites Experienced Vacuum Thermo-cycling," *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.*, vol. 25, no. 16, pp. 1647–1657, 2006.
- [5] F. E. Penado, "Effective Elastic Properties of Honeycomb Core with Fiber-Reinforced Composite Cells," *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, vol. 2013, no. October, pp. 89–96, 2013.
- [6] S. EZhandarov and E. Episanova, "Investigation of Load Transfer Between the Fiber and the Matrix," *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, no. S. EZhandarov, E. Episanova, E. Emsder, and J. EA. ENairn, 2005.
- [7] B. Pal, "Analytical Estimation of Elastic Properties of Polypropylene Fiber Matrix Composite by Finite Element Analysis," *Adv. Mater. Phys. Chem.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 23–30, 2012.
- [8] S. Bhaskara, R. Devireddy, and S. Biswas, "Effect of Fiber Geometry and Representative Volume Element on Elastic and Thermal Properties of Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Composites," *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, vol. 2014, 2014.
- [9] J. I. Cauich-Cupul, E. Pérez-Pacheco, A. Valadez-González, and P. J. Herrera-Franco, "Effect of moisture absorption on the micromechanical behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy matrix composites," *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 46, no. 20, pp. 6664–6672, 2011.
- [10] S. Zhu *et al.*, "Effect of moisture on the measured tensile strength of polyacrylonitrile carbon fibers," *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 51, no. 5, pp. 2371–2379, 2016.
- [11] D. J. Boll, W. D. Bascom, and B. Motiee, "Moisture absorption by structural epoxy-matrix carbon-fiber composites," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 253–273, 1985.
- [12] R. W. S. and D. A. D. A. Shanker, "Elastic properties of CYCOM 5320-1/T650 at elevated

- temperatures using response surface methodology,” *Compos. Hybrid, Multifunct. Mater. Springer*, vol. 4, pp. 29–37, 2015.
- [13] K. Jackson and M. Crabtree, “Autoclave quality composites tooling for composite from vacuum bag only processing,” *47 Th Int. SAMPE Symp. Exhib. 2002*, pp. 800–807, 2001.
- [14] B. W. Grimsley et al, “Elevated temperature, notched compression performance of out of autoclave processed composites,” *NASA Langley Res. Center, Hampton, VA, United States*, 2013.
- [15] J. K. Sutter et al, “Comparison of autoclave and out-of-autoclave composites,” *NASA Res. Cent.*, 2010.
- [16] Cauberghs and Julien, “Out-of-Autoclave Manufacturing of Aerospace Representative Parts,” 2012.
- [17] W. S. J. Tompkins SS, “Effects of thermal cycling on mechanical properties of Graphit Polimide,” *Mater. Lett.*, vol. 58, no. 12–13, pp. 1899–1902, 2004.
- [18] J. a. Sanborn and D. E. Morel, “Effects of Thermal Cycling on the Mechanical and Physical Properties of a Space Qualified Epoxy Adhesive,” *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 155–164, 1988.
- [19] Q. Yu *et al.*, “Effects of vacuum thermal cycling on mechanical and physical properties of high performance carbon/bismaleimide composite,” *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, vol. 130, no. 3, pp. 1046–1053, 2011.
- [20] I. Tsukrov, B. Drach, and T. S. Gross, “Effective stiffness and thermal expansion coefficients of unidirectional composites with fibers surrounded by cylindrically orthotropic matrix layers,” *Int. J. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 58, pp. 129–143, 2012.
- [21] R. Choqueuse, P.D., Davies, F., Baizeau, “Aging of Composites in Water: Comparison of Five Materials in Terms of Absorption Kinetics and Evolution of Mechanical Properties, High Temperature and Environmental Effects on Polymeric Composites,” *ASTM STP 1302*, vol. 2nd Volume, pp. 73–97, 1997.
- [22] Cyttec, “cycom® 5320-1 epoxy resin system technical data sheet,” 2015.